

formation of spin-paired complexes with octahedral structure. Their electronic spectra exhibit bands at 16130-15870, 19610-17860 and 26540-23260 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}$, ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$ transitions, respectively¹⁰. The magnetic moment of Fe(III) complexes lies in the 5.82-6.03 B.M. range suggesting the formation of spin-free complexes with octahedral structure¹¹. These complexes absorb at 15150-14710, 17540-16150 and 22990-22220 cm^{-1} attributable to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (P), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ (F) transitions, respectively¹². Co(III) and Fe(III) diphenates also form spin-paired and spin-free complexes¹³, respectively with *o*-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl.

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Chelates of Niobium(V) and Tantalum(V) Phenoxides with 2-Hydroxyacetophenone

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NIOBIUM(V) and tantalum(V) alkoxy compounds containing β -diketones and other related ligands of composition $M(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_4 \cdot L$, $M(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_3 \cdot L_2$ and $M(\text{OC}_2\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot L_3$ where L is benzoylacetone¹, ethyl benzoylacetate², methyl acetoacetate³ and ethyl acetoacetate have been reported. The corresponding acetylacetonate complexes are also known. α -Hydroxy ketones are also known to form a large number of donor-acceptor complexes with Lewis acids^{4,5}. However, a limited number of complexes are reported in the case of 2-hydroxyacetophenone (hap). Reactions of alkoxides of aluminium⁶, titanium⁷, zirconium⁸ and germanium⁹ with α -hydroxy

carboxylic acids and salicylic acids have been carried out. Tetramethoxy and triethoxy silanes are also known to react with these acids¹⁰. In the present investigations, an attempt has been made to isolate a few chelates of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) phenoxides with 2-hydroxyacetophenone.

Experimental

Niobium(V) and tantalum(V) phenoxides of composition $M(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_5$, $M\text{Cl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4$, $M\text{Cl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3$, $M\text{Cl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2$ and $M\text{Cl}_4(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)$ were prepared by published methods^{11,12}. 2-Hydroxyacetophenone (hapH) (A.R.) was used without further purification.

Compounds of composition $M(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_4 \cdot \text{hap}$ ($M = \text{Nb}$ or Ta) were prepared by refluxing either pentaphenoxides of the metals or tetraphenoxy metal(V) chlorides with the ligand. The compounds were isolated by the addition of petroleum ether or by cooling. Possible formation of the resulting compound may be visualized as follows :

Compounds of composition $M\text{Cl}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_3 \cdot \text{hap}$, $M\text{Cl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5)_2 \cdot \text{hap}$ and $M\text{Cl}_3(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_5) \cdot \text{hap}$ have been prepared by taking triphenoxy-, diphenoxy- and monophenoxy metal(V) chlorides and the ligand in benzene in 1 : 1 molar ratio and refluxing them till there was no evolution of hydrogen chloride gas. Stoichiometric composition of these compounds has been established by the estimation of metal and chlorine (Table 1).

Results and Discussion

All these compounds are fine crystalline solids and are fairly stable in dry air but change their colours on exposure to moisture. They are soluble in benzene, nitrobenzene and chloroform. Molar conductance values of millimolar solutions of the compounds in nitrobenzene (Table 1) suggest them to be non-electrolytes¹³. Molecular weight determinations of some of these compounds in nitrobenzene suggest them to be monomeric in nature.

The $\nu(\text{OH})$ stretching frequency at 3077 cm^{-1} in pure 2-hydroxyacetophenone¹⁴ (possibly due to intramolecular hydrogen bonding) is missing in all the complexes of phenoxides of niobium and tantalum which suggests that hydrogen of the hydroxyl group of the ligand is lost as hydrogen chloride gas. This is also supported by the observations that hydrogen chloride gas was evolved during the course of reaction and that phenol could be isolated from the filtrate of the complexes prepared from metal pentaphenoxides. However, no attempt was made for a quantitative estimation of phenol.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS OF NIOBIUM(V) AND TANTALUM(V) PHENOXIDES WITH 2-HYDROXYACETOPHENONE

Complex	Colour	m.p. (°C)	Analysis % ; Found/(Calcd.)			Molar conductance* (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)	Lowering in carbonyl stretching frequency ($\Delta\nu$)
			Metal	Cl	Molecular weight		
Nb(OC ₆ H ₅) ₄ .hap	Yellow	84(d)	15.17 (15.50)	—	580 (600)	2.14	60
NbCl(OC ₆ H ₅) ₃ .hap	Yellow	112	16.95 (17.14)	6.28 (6.54)	563 (542.5)	2.27	68
NbCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ .hap	Reddish brown	78(d)	18.68 (19.17)	14.24 (14.62)	500 (485)	1.98	65
NbCl ₃ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₁ .hap	Yellow orange	104	21.33 (21.75)	24.61 (24.91)	451 (427.5)	2.63	70
Ta(OC ₆ H ₅) ₄ .hap	Lemon yellow	115	26.08 (26.31)	—	650 (688)	1.71	60
TaCl(OC ₆ H ₅) ₃ .hap	Lemon yellow	120(d)	28.44 (28.70)	5.36 (5.63)	—	1.85	62
TaCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ .hap	Yellow	110	31.34 (31.59)	12.14 (12.39)	533 (573)	1.89	66
TaCl ₃ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₁ .hap	Yellow	140(d)	34.72 (35.11)	20.32 (20.66)	530 (515.5)	1.97	65

d—decompose.

*in nitrobenzene.

Coordination from oxygen of the phenolic group of 2-hydroxyacetophenone to the central metal is further supported by the lowering ($\Delta\nu$) of the carbonyl (C=O) stretching frequency at 1640 cm⁻¹ in pure 2-hydroxyacetophenone¹⁵, by ~60-70 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes (Table 1). Similar observations have been made earlier also in the complexes of tartrate¹⁶.

Attention has also been focussed on the metal-oxygen stretching modes which are expected to fall in the 400-600 cm⁻¹ region. The bands around 540-550 cm⁻¹ in the case of parent niobium phenoxides and around 510-520 cm⁻¹ in the case of

tantalum phenoxides assigned to bridging M M modes, respectively¹⁷, appear to have disappeared on complexation. Instead, sharp bands at 570-580 cm⁻¹ in case of niobium and at 540-550 cm⁻¹ in case of tantalum compounds have been observed and may be assigned to terminal $\nu(M-O)$ stretching modes¹⁷. Thus, complete absence of absorption

bands due to bridging M M modes and appearance of sharp intense bands due to terminal $\nu(M-O)$ modes suggest that dimeric structure of the parent phenoxides gets ruptured on complexation. Similar observations have been made in case of alkoxides¹⁵.

It is interesting to note that though these metals are well known to abstract oxygen from the ligand resulting in the formation of M=O bonds^{18,19}, no oxygen abstraction has been observed in any of the compounds isolated in the present studies as is evident from the fact that no absorption band around 920-940 cm⁻¹, that could be assigned to Nb=O or Ta=O stretching modes, has been observed in the spectra of these complexes.

In the low frequency infrared spectra of the compounds isolated in the present studies, sharp intense bands in the region 350-360 cm⁻¹ in case of niobium and 330-340 cm⁻¹ in case of tantalum compounds [except in case of compound M(OC₆H₅)₄.hap] may be assigned to terminal $\nu(M-Cl)$ stretching modes in an octahedral environment²⁰. Thus, based on elemental analysis, cryoscopic, conductance and infrared spectral studies, a possible octahedral structure for all these compounds may be proposed.

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salts were all B.D.H., AnalaR grade samples. Ethanol solvent was purified as described earlier⁶.

The experimental method consisted of the well known Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁷. In the titrations of the potassium salts of Schiff bases derived from the dibasic aspartic and glutamic acids, 0.2 M HClO₄ was used instead of 0.1 M HClO₄.

Stabilities of Some Bivalent Metal Complexes of Salicylaldehyde and Substituted Salicylaldehyde-Aminoacid Schiff Bases

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SOME bivalent metal complexes of Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde and glycine have been investigated by Eichhorn and Marchand¹ spectrophotometrically and by Leussing *et al.*² potentiometrically in aqueous solution. Apart from these, there is not much report on the complexes of other amino acids. We report here the results of our studies involving the amino acids, glycine, α -alanine, aspartic acid and glutamic acid, and aromatic aldehydes, such as salicylaldehyde, 5-methyl-, 5-chloro- and 5-bromo-salicylaldehydes. The systems involving salicylaldehyde have been studied both in aqueous as well as in 50% (v/v) ethanolic media, while, the substituted salicylaldehyde systems have been studied only in the latter.

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde (E. Merck) used was freshly distilled under reduced pressure. The 5-methyl-, 5-chloro- and 5-bromo-salicylaldehydes were prepared by reported methods³⁻⁵.

Among the α -amino acids, glycine and glutamic acids were E. Merck products and α -alanine and aspartic acids were of B.D.H. make. The metal

Results and Discussion

The stabilities of the metal complexes of any given ligand depend on the magnitude of the acid dissociation constant of the ligand. They have been calculated in this work as practical protonation constants, according to the method of Irving and Rossotti⁶. Table 1 summarises the acid dissociation constants determined in this work, some in aqueous and some in 50% ethanolic medium. The pK_1^H values listed are associated with the dissociation of the carboxylic proton and the pK_2^H with that of the hydroxylic proton.

The calculation of $\bar{n}_A$, $\bar{n}$ and pL have been made by considering the ligands as biprotic. The $\log K_1$ and $\log \beta_2$ values have been obtained both by the half-integral method as well as the least square method, where the range of $\bar{n}$ lay between 0 and 2.0. In other cases, they were obtained by the half-integral method only.

Table 2 summarises the stability constants of the metal complexes of some of the Schiff bases studied in aqueous medium, while Table 3 summarises the results obtained in 50% ethanolic medium at 30°.

Cu(II) seems to show little tendency to form 1 : 2 complexes in aqueous medium, in contrast with Ni(II), Zn(II) and Co(II). This, however, is not true of the 50% ethanolic medium. This may probably be due to specific solvent effects. Zn(II) alone seems to have a tendency to form 1 : 3 complexes both in aqueous and 50% ethanolic media. It has been pointed out on the basis of its magnetic moment⁸ that Zn(II) is the only one that cannot form octahedral complexes. On both these grounds, it

TABLE 1—ACID DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF SCHIFF BASES FORMED BY SALICYLALDEHYDE AND AMINOACIDS AT 20°, 30° AND 40°

	pK_1^H			pK_2^H		
	20°	30°	40°	20°	30°	40°
In aqueous medium						
i) Salicylidene-glycine	10.01	9.80	9.74	8.96	8.25	8.12
ii) Salicylidene- α -alanine	10.37	9.89	9.53	8.23	7.91	7.97
iii) Salicylidene-aspartic acid	—	9.77	—	—	7.92	—
iv) Salicylidene-glutamic acid	—	9.49	—	—	7.79	—
In 50% aqueous ethanol medium						
i) Salicylidene-glycine	—	9.92	—	—	8.35	—
ii) 5-Methylsalicylidene-glycine	—	9.80	—	—	8.40	—
iii) 5-Chloro-salicylidene-glycine	—	9.78	—	—	7.65	—
iv) 5-Bromo-salicylidene-glycine	—	9.57	—	—	7.63	—